

Composition of Jute Fibre. Part II. Hemicelluloses.

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It is generally assumed that jute cellulose is associated with "hemicelluloses"—pentosans, hexosans or hexopentosans, which are generally insoluble in water but soluble in alkali and are readily hydrolysed by acids. No precise information as to the nature of these carbohydrates accompanying jute cellulose is however available. The following investigations were undertaken with the object of obtaining a peep into the nature of so-called hemicelluloses in jute.

In order to avoid complications due to the presence of lignone matter, it is necessary to free the fibre from the last traces of lignone. Different investigators who studied hemicelluloses in wood, straw or other lignocelluloses, delignified their fibres by the usual methods of treatment with bisulphite, alkali or chlorine. All these delignifying agents however not only remove a considerable portion of hemicelluloses but affect them chemically as well. For satisfactory investigation of hemicelluloses, a reagent is necessary which, while removing the lignone matter completely, would leave the non-celluloses intact.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 339) it was found that hemicelluloses remained practically unaffected when jute fibre was delignified with 2.5% chlorine peroxide solution. Jute lignone was completely oxidised by this reagent into water-soluble products which could be easily washed off.

Delignification by Chlorine Peroxide.—It has been found that delignification is effected more efficiently by the action of chlorine peroxide gas on moist jute instead of its solution in water or acetic acid as recommended by Schmidt and Graumann (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 1860). To remove lignone completely, either a single exposure for two or three days or two exposures, each of twenty-four hours' duration, to a slow stream of chlorine peroxide gas have been found most effective. A slow stream of chlorine peroxide may easily be obtained by the action of dilute sulphuric acid on potassium chlorate and oxalic acid at room temperature (25-30°) with slight previous heating. If sodium chlorate is used in place of the potassium salt, more dilute acid has to be used while the slight previous warming may be dispensed with. The process goes on smoothly, without any attention as

regards the control of temperature, strength of solution and other factors while the worker is saved from the danger of exposing himself to the highly irritating fumes of chlorine peroxide when handling the solution. The tedious process of obtaining a concentrated solution of the gas in ice-cooled water may thus be avoided. Delignification is also more effective while the furfural-yielding complexes are left practically intact.

Extraction of Hemicelluloses.—The delignified jute was extracted successively with (a) benzene, (b) 95% alcohol, (c) boiling water, and (d) 17.5% caustic soda. The extracted material was then isolated either by evaporation of the solvent or by concentration and addition of alcohol. The hemicelluloses thus obtained were purified by repeated precipitation with alcohol from their solutions. The solid substances were then hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (2.5%), and the excess of the acid removed as barium sulphate. The filtrate was then concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrup which was tested for different carbohydrates and was also used for their quantitative estimation.

Carbohydrates found in the Hemicelluloses.

Galactose.—For the detection and estimation of galactose in the presence of galacturonic acid, the oxidation method was found to be unsuitable, as both the substances gave mucic acid on oxidation. A satisfactory separation was however effected by the insolubility of barium galacturonate in 80% alcohol which however dissolved galactose (O'Dwyer, *Biochem. J.*, 1926, 20, 656).

Schmidt and others (*Cellulosechem.*, 1929, 10, 126) investigated the presence of galactose in different cellulose materials but in all cases it was found absent. This was perhaps due not to the actual absence of galactose in the original material but to the fact that galactose, linked with galacturonic acid, was easily removed by sodium sulphite treatment to which they subjected the delignified fibres.

Fructose.—Fairly large amount of fructose (6.3% in the alkali extract) has been found present in jute. This has been confirmed by a large number of qualitative tests and estimated in the presence of aldoses by the method of Willstätter and Schüdel (*Ber.*, 1928, 51, 780).

“Uronic” Acids.—Attention is due to the large amount of “uronic” acids (e.g., galacturonic acid) in different fractions. Galacturonic

acid reduces Fehling's solution readily and gives all the colour reactions for pentoses and probably for this reason its presence in ligno-celluloses has escaped notice. It was first assumed that the large amount of uronic acids found in these experiments were due to the oxidising action of chlorine peroxide on jute. This was however found not to be the case; for, the furfural content and uronic acids of jute were 10.06% and 8.08% respectively, while those of the delignified fibre were 8.8% and 9.01% (calculated on jute) respectively. It is therefore evident that neither the furfural-yielding complexes nor the uronic acids were seriously affected by the action of chlorine peroxide.

Galacturonic acid has been identified by qualitative tests. Attempts were made to estimate it by the following methods:

- (1) Direct titration with alkali.
- (2) Oxidation to mucic acid.
- (3) Estimation of carbon dioxide evolved by treatment with 12% hydrochloric acid (Tollens and Le Fevré, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4513; Nanji, Paton and Ling, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 253T).

The titration method was found unsatisfactory as it did not give concordant results in all cases while the mucic acid method could not be applied owing to the presence of galactose. Estimation of carbon dioxide was however found quite satisfactory and this method has been therefore used in these experiments. The amounts of uronic acids (calculated as galacturonic acid) found in different fractions are stated below:

Alcohol extract	..	1.66%	(calculated on delignified jute).
Water extract	..	3.79%	
Alkali extract	...	1.79%	

It is interesting to note that on decarboxylation of uronic acids, which may easily take place in plants by the action of enzymes, pentoses are formed according to the reaction,

Xylose would thus be formed from glycuronic acid and arabinose from galacturonic acid. These acids may therefore play an important part in the formation of pentoses and perhaps also of lignone in plants (Ehrlich, *Chem.-Ztg.*, 1917, 41, 197).

The furfural yield of jute has so far been interpreted to indicate its pectosan content, though some investigators (Schwalbe, *Z. angew.*

Chem., 1918, 31, 51; Hägglund and Klingstedt, *Cellulosechem.*, 1924, 8, 58) have doubted that pentosans alone are responsible for the whole of furfural yield. In a recent paper (*Ber.*, 1925, 68, 1584), Schwalbe has shown that a small fraction of the furfural yield of straw is due to glycuronic acid. It is evident that in the case of jute also, an appreciable fraction of the furfural yield must be attributed to uronic acids. If the furfural yield of uronic anhydride is taken as 16.6% (Norman, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 525), 1.22% of the furfural content of jute fibre (uronic acids 8.08%) must be due to the presence of uronic acids. As the furfural content of jute has been found to be 10.06%, about 1/8th of this figure is to be attributed to uronic acids and the rest to pentosans.

Pentososes.—Arabinose and xylose have been identified by usual colorimetric tests as well as by the preparation of suitable derivatives. It will be apparent from the remarks made above, that the present method of determining pentososes from the furfural content is inaccurate and should always be supplemented by a determination of uronic carbon dioxide. From the difference of the total furfural content and that due to uronic acids, the pentosan content can be calculated. As has already been noted, the pentososes may have been formed in nature by decarboxylation of uronic acids.

Pectin.—The high uronic acid content of jute is rather significant and may indicate the presence of pectic substances, as galacturonic acid has been found by Ehrlich (*loc. cit.*) to be the main constituent of pectin. On a search being made, pectins have actually been found in appreciable amounts in jute and have been estimated as insoluble calcium salt after extraction with three different solvents, *i.e.* (1) water, (2) 0.5% oxalic acid, and (3) 0.5% ammonium oxalate solution.

The methods available for the estimation of pectin are however empirical in nature. From the wide difference between the uronic acid content (8.08%) and the pectin content (1.47%) as determined by calcium salt method, it would appear that the total amount of pectin is not obtained as insoluble calcium salt. It may be noted that the calcium-magnesium salt of pectic acid as isolated by Ehrlich (*loc. cit.*) is soluble in water. In the course of these investigations it was found that the water extract of jute, after separation of insoluble calcium pectate, had a methoxyl value of which, as in the case of pectin, 50% was in the form of ether linkage and 50% of ester linkage. Thus both the methoxyl and the carbon dioxide

values indicate that insoluble calcium salt cannot be a quantitative measure of pectin, unless pectin is defined in a special sense.

It has been found that pectins and hemicelluloses of jute may be removed almost completely by treatment with water in an autoclave at 2—3 atmos. for a period of four hours. The residual cellulose is similar in property to α -cellulose and found to be completely free from uronic carbon dioxide, the furfural content being as low as 1.58%. This figure compares satisfactorily with furfural content of α -cellulose in jute, 1.08% found by Chowdhury and Mazumdar (*loc. cit.*) and 2.4% found by Lehne and Scheppmann (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1925, 38, 93).

Finally it is interesting to note that when the alkali extract of delignified jute fibre is neutralised with acetic acid, no precipitate is obtained. If any water-insoluble hexosans or pentosans were present in jute, these would be extracted by alkali though not likely to be hydrolysed by it, and on neutralisation, should form a precipitate. The absence of any water-insoluble hexopentosans suggests that they are either present in jute in comparatively low molecular weights so as to be highly soluble or that they are in chemical combination with the uronic or pectic acids in which form they are soluble in water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The middle portion of the fibre was taken, rejecting one foot from below and above. The fibres were then loosened by mechanical means and washed with Pear's soap to remove dust and adhering oils and fats, dried and cut into small pieces.

Jute, cut into small pieces, was extracted with chloroform to remove resin and fat. It was then subjected to the action of chlorine peroxide gas in a glass tower or a series of glass towers, until the fibre was perfectly white. The results of analysis of the original and the delignified jute are given below:

	<i>Raw jute.</i>	<i>Delignified jute.</i>
α -Cellulose	... 67.25%	67.25% (calculated on raw jute).
Lignin	.. 16.21%	nil.
Furfural	... 10.08%	10.31% " " "
Resin and fat	.. 1.12%	—
Ash	... 0.501%	—
Moisture	.. 15.55%	—
Uronic acids	... 8.08%	10.36% " " "

Fractional Extraction of Hemicelluloses from Delignified Jute.

1. *Benzene Extraction.*—Delignified jute was first extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet for ten or twelve hours. On evaporating the colourless extract, a viscous oily product of characteristic woody odour was obtained. Yield—0·51%. The product was evidently resinous in nature but, owing to the small yield, was not further investigated.

2. *Alcohol Extraction.*—The fibre was then extracted with 95% alcohol. A brown mass was obtained on evaporation of the extract under reduced pressure and was found to be very similar to pectin. Yield—2·52%.

3. *Water Extraction.*—The fibre was next extracted twice with boiling water under reflux. The extract was filtered through cloth, concentrated to a syrup over a small flame and poured in a large amount of 95% alcohol when a sticky mass was obtained. This was allowed to settle, decanted and on washing with absolute alcohol and ether, was obtained as a dry amorphous powder. The yield of this alcohol-insoluble product from the first extraction was 12·66% and from the second extraction 4·35%. That these extracts consist very largely of pentoses is indicated by the high furfural value, the former giving 34·56% and the latter 30·12% furfural.

It may however be noted that a portion of the water extract, when poured in alcohol, remained in alcoholic solution and was obtained as a brown product on evaporation. The yield of this alcohol soluble product from the first extract was 5·3% (furfural, 15·88%) and from the second extract 0·72%.

4. *Alkali Extraction.*—The above extractions were followed by a treatment of the residual jute with 17·5% caustic soda. The brown extract was acidified with acetic acid and added to an excess of 95% alcohol. The white precipitate thus obtained was washed with alcohol and ether, and dried in the usual manner at a low temperature. Yield 8·6% (furfural 28·12%). Pentosans are therefore an important constituent of this extract though a part of the furfural must be attributed to uronic acids which, as estimated from carbon dioxide value, amounted to 20·09%.

As in the case of water extract, a portion of the alkali extract also remained in alcoholic solution which amounted to 6·32%.

Examination of Different Extracts.

The solid alcohol-insoluble substances obtained from water and alkali extracts were hydrolysed by treatment with 2.5% sulphuric acid for 11-12 hours on water-bath, and the acid then removed with barium carbonate. The brownish filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrup which was then examined for different carbohydrates and acids in the manner described below. When testing for mannose, hydrochloric acid (d 1.025) was used instead of sulphuric acid to hydrolyse the substance.

Tests for Identification of Carbohydrates.

Galactose.—(a) Phenylhydrazone, recrystallised from dilute alcohol, melted at 159-160°.

(b) A portion of the syrup was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and extracted with 80% alcohol which dissolved galactose but not barium galacturonate. Alcohol was then evaporated off and the resulting syrup oxidised with nitric acid of sp. gr. 1.15 at 85°. Mucic acid was thus obtained which, recrystallised from hot water, melted at 218° with decomposition. As mucic acid is formed also by the oxidation of galacturonic acid, its previous separation is necessary. Galactose was identified both in water and alkali extracts.

Fructose.—(a) A reagent consisting of cupric hydrate, glycooll, and potassium carbonate solutions was reduced at 15–20° in eight hours. Sugars other than fructose reduce this reagent only above 40°. This was verified by artificial mixtures of different sugars prepared in the laboratory.

(b) Pinoff's test which is a specific reaction for ketoses indicated the presence of fructose. This was also verified by artificial mixture of sugars.

(c) To a small quantity of the syrup, 3 to 5 drops of 2*N*-potassium hydroxide were added followed by 0.5–1 g. of solid caustic potash when a red band round the solid alkali was obtained (Ekkert. *Pharm. Zentr.* 1928, 69, 805).

(d) *o*-Methylphenylhydrazone, recrystallised from dilute alcohol, melted at 158-159°.

Fructose was found mainly in the alkali extract.

Glucose.—(a) Barfoed's reagent, which serves as a delicate test for glucose, indicated its presence.

(b) The presence of glucose was also confirmed by oxidation to saccharic acid. This was possible as mannose was found absent when tested by Schorger's method.

Xylose.—The syrup was evaporated to dryness in vacuum and extracted with absolute alcohol, the extract being tested for xylose. It was found largely in the alkali extract.

(a) Phenyllosazone, recrystallised from dilute alcohol, melted at 159-160°.

(b) Characteristic prismatic needles were obtained by Bertrand and Tollen's test.

(c) *p*-Nitrophenylhydrazone, recrystallised from alcohol, melted at 154-155°.

Arabinose.—(a) *p*-Bromophenylhydrazone, recrystallised from absolute alcohol, melted at 158-160°.

(b) Diphenylhydrazone of arabinose was also prepared.

Galacturonic acid.—This acid was found both in water and alkali extracts. Its presence was indicated by the following tests.

(a) The syrup gave a soluble barium salt.

(b) The calcium salt was obtained as microscopic prisms.

(c) The cadmium salt formed needles slightly soluble in water.

Estimation of Carbohydrates.

Galactose.—For the estimation of this sugar, it was freed from galacturonic acid whose barium salt was insoluble in alcohol. It was then oxidised to mucic acid by nitric acid (*d* 1.15) at 85°. The mucic acid was weighed and galactose calculated from Van der Haar's table. It was found that the water extract contained 14.12% and the alkali extract 1.78% galactose.

Fructose.—Fructose was estimated by Willstätter and Schüedell's method (*loc. cit.*) which consists in the oxidation of aldoses by means of iodine in alkaline solution leaving the ketoses unaffected.

Total reducing sugars	...	...	...	64.27%
Total aldoses	...	...	...	57.87%
Fructose (difference)	...	...	...	6.40%

Galacturonic Acid.—This acid was estimated from the amount of carbon dioxide evolved by treatment with 12% hydrochloric acid. The carbon dioxide was led into a standard baryta solution, the excess of which was titrated in the usual manner. The uronic acid was calculated from the following equation :

It was found that the syrup obtained from water extract had 29.92% and that from alkali extract had 20.09% uronic acids. A control experiment was made with unhydrolysed water extract which was found to contain 32.84% uronic acids. A portion of these acids was evidently destroyed by 2.5% sulphuric acid used for the purpose of hydrolysis.

Pectic Substances in Jute.

Pectic matters of delignified jute were extracted by treatment with (a) water, (b) 0.5% oxalic acid solution, and (c) 0.5% ammonium oxalate solution at 85° for twenty-four hours at a stretch. It was found that intermittent extraction with oxalic acid hydrolysed pectic matters. The extracts were concentrated over a small flame and poured in a large amount of alcohol, the oxalic acid extract being neutralised with ammonia before concentration. In the case of ammonium oxalate and oxalic acid extracts, alcohol acidified with hydrochloric acid was used. The precipitates were filtered and washed with acidified alcohol until free from oxalic acid, washed again with absolute alcohol and ether and dried. The actual pectin content of these alcohol insoluble extracts was then determined by the calcium pectate method of Carré and Haynes (*Biochem. J.*, 1922, 16, 60). It may be noted that the alcoholic extract of delignified jute was also found to contain pectic substances. The following table gives the quantities of pectin, estimated by the calcium pectate method, in different extracts and also its other characteristics.

		Cal. pectate (calc. on delig. jute).	Methoxyl.	Furfural.	Uronic acids.
Alcohol extract	...	0.68%	7.15%	7.36%	30.22%
Water extract (85°)	...	1.10%	14.61%	36.91%	38.64%
Oxalic acid extract	...	1.67%	5.0%	18.61%	34.36%
Amm. oxalate extract	..	1.65%	6.87%	24.16%	37.88%

Examination of Water and Alkali Extracts freed from Pectin.

Pectin was removed from the extracts as insoluble calcium pectate by the addition of lime water. The filtrate was neutralised with acetic acid, concentrated and poured in a large amount of alcohol. In the case of alkali extract, it was neutralised with acetic acid before addition of lime water and the pectin-free substances were purified by repeated precipitation with alcohol. It was found that the water extract, when freed from insoluble calcium pectate, had a total methoxyl value of 12.2%, of which, half (6.0%) was easily removed by hydrolysis at ordinary temperature with 0.4N-caustic soda and was evidently in the form of ester linkage, the rest of the methoxyl (6.2%) being present as ether linkage. It would thus appear that if methoxyl number be an indication of the presence of pectin, the whole of it was not precipitated as insoluble calcium pectate. The alkali extract, freed from calcium pectate, gave 4.9% methoxyl, of which none was removed by hydrolysis with dilute alkali, the ester linkage being evidently absent in this instance.

Removal of Pectin and Hemicelluloses by Water at High Temperature.

A quantity of delignified jute after extraction with alcohol and water, was treated with water in an autoclave at three atmospheres for five hours. After removing the brown extract, the fibre was washed and dried. It was found to be practically free from any carbon-dioxide-yielding constituent while the furfural content was only 1.58%. The sample was evidently free from uronic acids and pectic substances responsible for carbon dioxide or from hemicelluloses yielding furfural.